

OBJECTIVES AND OBJECTIVES OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL RELATIONS WITH EMPLOYEES

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Abstract: This article discusses the organizational basis of the audit of financial relations with employees in enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: employee, financial relations, financial reporting, organizational support, statistics, control, audit.

Introduction. The audit of financial relations with employees includes calculations with employees in respect of wages, with accountable persons and other transactions with employees in respect of salaries with employees and hired persons. These calculations are carried out mainly in cash and pointless form. Therefore, financial relations with employees are a sphere in which many mistakes are made deliberately or without knowledge, and require the auditor to pay special attention to the examination.

Financial relations with employees the main purpose of conducting audit is to formulate an opinion on the reliability of the department in which the accounts receivable and liabilities related to the circulation of financial relations with employees in the accounting report are reflected, the compliance of the method of accounting and taxation with the applicable normative documents and the social protection of

It is a very important factor in determining the following main objectives in carrying out audit of the financial relations with the employees. (See Table 1).

Table 1

The main objectives of auditing financial relations with employees

The purpose of the audit of financial relations with employees is to determine the following:	
Fullness	<i>-the fact that all financial relations with these employees are reflected in the accounting report, there are no accounting records that are not taken into account</i>
	<i>-the presence of obligations on the date of the</i>

Existing	<i>conclusion of this balance sheet in financial relations with employees (wages, accrued amounts, etc.), and the fact that this obligation is greater than the sum</i>
Rights and obligations	<i>-the legality and correctness of the amounts of obligations related to financial relations with these employees, based on the criteria of three (form, legality and fairness)</i>
Assessments	<i>-the fact that the obligations to financial relations with these employees are assessed in accordance with the normative documents</i>
Lightness	<i>-this is the correct calculation of the salary and the amounts withheld from it, the amount of daily expenses on the service trip, etc., the compliance of accounting information with the data in the synthetic and analytical accounting registers</i>
Limitation of the accounting period	<i>-this is when all the obligations to the financial relations with the employees are reflected in the same accounting period</i>
Presentation and statement	<i>-the fact that all obligations to financial relations with these employees are described, categorized and presented in accordance with the normative acts on the account and the report.</i>

In order to achieve the set objective, the following table 2 tasks should be solved in the audit.

Table 2

**Financial relationships with employees
tasks to be solved in audit**

Functions of the audit	Questions on the audit of financial relations with employees
1. To take into account the attitude audit towards financial relations with employees and to assess the state of the effectiveness of internal control	<p>Availability and analysis of documents that determine the payment of Labor and the issuance of accountable sums.</p> <p>Evaluation of the organization of documentation of Personnel, time of work and the account of the produced product (work, service).</p> <p>The presence of a classifier (categorizer) of the types of amounts that are charged and deducted from wages.</p> <p>Control over the issuance of wages and accountable amounts.</p> <p>Compliance of reporting indicators with data of synthetic and analytical accounting registers.</p>

<p>2. Checking the reliability of the data of accounts and reports on the calculation of wages with employees.</p>	<p>Accuracy of the calculation of wages by types of remuneration. The correctness of the amounts withheld from the salary. The rationale for adding wage costs to the cost structure. The calculation of wages and the amount withheld from it are reflected in the accounting registers. The correctness of taking into account the total income for the purpose of taxation.</p>
<p>3. Correctness of calculation of accounts with funds outside the state budget, Social Security and supply funds</p>	<p>The correctness of determining the base of the calculation of payments to non-budgetary social insurance and supply funds. The correctness of reflecting the calculations with social insurance and supply funds on the account.</p>
<p>4. Checking the reliability of accounting and reporting information on accounts with accountable persons.</p>	<p>It is based on the provision of chalk to accountable persons. Timely submission of reports of joints. The fact that the use of accountable sums is justified by documents. The rationale for the inclusion of accountable sums in the structure of costs. The correctness of taxation. The correctness of reflecting the accounts with the accountable persons in the accounting account.</p>
<p>5. Smoothing the reliability of information on the accounts and reporting on other financial transactions with employees.</p>	<p>The correctness of taking into account the calculations for the goods sold on credit. Legality and justification of lending. The correctness of taking into account the calculations on the given debts. Full implementation of the deficit and theft on the responsibility of the guilty persons. Correctness of taking into account the calculations on the compensation of material damage.</p>
<p>5. Smoothing the reliability of information on the accounts and reporting on other financial transactions with employees.</p>	<p>Generalization and analysis of materials of working documents on examination. To determine the magnitude (seriousness) of the error. To determine the impact of errors on report reliability.</p>

The Auditor should pay special attention to and make sure that there are no serious errors in the reporting indicators during the examination. Evidence-a database of information that is formed from different sources is used to collect evidence. The Auditor collects a package of normative documents, synthetic and analytical accounting registers and initial documents necessary to verify internal accounting records before starting the audit, and then analyzes them by comparing them with the Ozoro.

The package of normative documents regulating the rules established for the reflection and taxation of financial relations with employees in accounting is formed by the auditor taking into account the characteristics of the client-enterprise activity and requires the proper use of them.

Synthetic and analytical account registers on the accounts of the branches that take into account the financial relations with employees are applied to the form of accounts used in the Enterprise (Journal-order, memorial-order, table-automated, etc.) will depend. For example, in enterprises, where accounting is carried out in the form of a journal-order, 7-ask, 8-ask and 10-ask Journal-orders, in the form of tabulated (or computerized) – 4210-"payment of wages on Labor", 6510-"payments on insurance", 6710-"calculations with employees on wages", 6720-"deponent wages", 4220-"points for service trips", 4230-"points for general economic expenses", 4290-"other contributions to employees", 6870-"debts from accountable persons", 4710- "Debts of employees on the goods sold on credit", 4720-" debts of employees on the given debtor", 4730-" debts of employees on compensation for material damage"and 4790-" other debts of employees " debit and credit facilities on the accounts receivable are checked.

In the conditions of the market economy, there are new infrastructures inherent in it. One of these is auditing and auditing activities. In developed countries of the market economy, auditing has existed for a long time, this concept has been covered in different ways. For example, in England, when an audit is said, it is understood that the audit of the financial statements of economic entities and express its independent opinion about it by the auditor. In the opinion of the American Association of accountants, the audit was viewed as a system of collection and evaluation of object data on economic events and events. As stated in the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on auditing activity"dated May 26, 2000 and in the provisions of the national standards of auditing activity," audit is carried out in accordance with the correctness of the financial statements of economic entities by persons granted certain powers, the extent to which they comply with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is recognized as" verification carried out in order to determine the correct compliance of accounting and financial statements with the requirements for proceedings as well as the requirements of other documents". The Audit also includes services that are provided on the basis of a contract with the client. The audit is conducted by a specialist who has the right to be guided by the activities of the auditor. Thus, an audit is an examination of the complete and accurate structure of the financial statements of an enterprise.

Audit activity is an entrepreneurial activity, it consists of activities aimed at independent examination of financial statements of economic entities, payment accounting documents, tax returns and other financial obligations. In addition,

through the audit, the following activities are also carried out again. иқтисодий субъектнинг активлари ва пасивларини баҳолаш;

- establishment of declarations on income of the enterprise;
- provide advice on finance, tax, banking and other economic legislation;
- training of personnel and others.

In the normative documents related to the activities of the auditor, the following provisions on his activities are prescribed::

- free choice of economic subject;
- absence of kinship and other relations with the client;
- the contractual relationship between the auditor and the client gives the auditor the opportunity to choose the client himself, that is, he must be independent of any instructions of the state bodies;
- to achieve the elimination of identified deficiencies;
- auditors and audit firms are only allowed to engage in activities established by law.

Financial relations with employees the purpose of the audit is to perform specific tasks established by law, to ensure compliance of financial relations with employees with the existing legislation and legal acts, as well as regulatory regulation, to fulfill contractual obligations between the enterprise and its employees. During the Audit, the financial statements of the economic entities, their authenticity are determined and they are checked for compliance with the normative documents of the financial and economic operations carried out by the liquidator.

The duties of the auditor is an expression of the fact that the financial relations between the employees are correctly reflected in the balance sheet, in the report on financial results, as well as the accuracy of their information in the explanatory letters are covered by the auditor through the auditor.

Auditor bunda should pay attention to the following:

- to the extent that the financial relationship between the employees and the employees is properly reflected in the report;
- information on the basis of the financial relationship between the employees and the employees on the basis of all the information on the account;
- in assessing the compliance with the legislation, it is necessary to pay special attention to the employees of the financial relations and the main documents.

The Auditor will examine the following in order to achieve the main objective and draw conclusions: financial relations with employees correspond to the current account data of The Associated reports, the correct performance of the tasks assigned to the enterprise;

- financial relationship with employees availability of grounds for inclusion of information in reports;
- the relevance of financial relations with employees to this enterprise;
- the correct assessment of all the accounts of financial relations with employees;
- to pay attention to the fact that all the indicators of the financial relationship with the employees are fully included in the financial statements.

The results of this study show that the normative acts, special literature and academic performance are expressed in a variety of audit, auditing activities and auditing activities.

Auditing activities include auditing and auditing professional services (Chart 1):

1-drawing. Content of auditing activities

Direct audit, in turn, is conducted in two forms (2-th drawing). Mandatory and initiative-style forms of auditing differ from each other depending on the customers, objects of audit, purpose and functions assigned. Similar auditing checks will also have different types of customers.

2-drawing. Forms of auditing audit

In the normative documents of the Republic there are specific objects of audit carried out in a mandatory and initiative manner. Types of Audit are also classified depending on the stages of its development (Figure 3):

3-drawing. Classification of audit by stage of development

In contrast to the above, the types of audits differ depending on their objects and are divided into the following (Figure 4):

4-drawing. Types of audit objects

It should also be separately recognized that the law "on auditing activities" adopted in our republic does not specify the division of audit into external and internal audit, the differences between them. We believe that these issues should be expressed in the new edition of this law.

Prof. K.B.Urazov explains the content of internal and external audit as follows: "internal audit is a means of internal control in economic entities with a lower tier of the economy. External audit is a means of Control conducted by independent audit organizations from the point of view of the interests of the state and economic entities . Many such examples can be cited.

In the special literature, the meaning and essence of internal and external audios are expressed in different ways. Included prof. V.I.Podolsky believes that internal audit is an examination conducted in the interests of the heads of enterprises, the main purpose of which is to help the employees of the enterprise to effectively start their duties . The well-known scientist prof. M.M.To "audit is the study by independent qualified specialists of the financial report of an enterprise or its associated financial information, reports or information for the purpose of

drawing conclusions on the degree of compliance with the law and other normative acts," laxojaeva said

tariff provides . In this matter, the author's opinion refers more to external audit.

The findings of the study showed that the organization and conduct of auditing services in enterprises is relatively difficult to experience. This issue is especially evident in the organization of internal audit in enterprises and the training and involvement of specialists for them.

The findings of the study show that the financial relationship between employees and the methodological basis of auditing is not fully scientifically developed. The following methods of auditing are widely used in the audit processes related to the financial relationship between employees:

- documentation;
- evaluation;
- group;
- inventory;
- calculation;
- accounting balance sheet;
- comparison (comparison);
- bills and double entry;
- expertise;
- audit analysis;
- use of reporting data;
- other methods.

In our opinion, the methods used in the audit should be determined depending on the type, objects, functions of the audit, the type of audit. Due to the wide application of computer technology in economic processes, it is expedient to make effective use of computerized methods of auditing.

The financial relationship between employees and the functions of The Associated audit will again include the following:

- to make suggestions to the management body of the enterprise in order to eliminate the shortcomings identified as a result of the audit of the financial relationship with the employees;
- control over the compliance with the accounting policy in the enterprise;
 - to ensure proper formalization and accounting of accounting facilities;
 - control over the execution of the enterprise business plan;
 - to ensure that accounting is carried out in accordance with the requirements of national standards;

- to check the compliance of the financial report with the current account information;
- the financial relationship between employees is to address the identified deficiencies in the audit.

In the Audit process, the following are identified: корхонада бухгалтерия ҳисобининг ташкил қилиниш шакли;

- availability of "Account policy" in the economic entity;
- distribution of duties to accounting personnel;
- the fact that internal documents are recorded in a separate book;
- level of performance of assigned tasks;
- the presence of activities aimed at eliminating identified shortcomings (decisions, orders adopted);
- compliance of financial reporting information with current accounting information;
- wide introduction of advanced forms and methods of accounting;
- buxgateriya Accounting Service employee's non-resettlement rate.

Thus, through audit, the financial relations that will be with all employees carried out in the enterprise must be controlled. The Auditor will pay attention to the same when familiarizing with the control in the enterprise and assessing it:

- the degree of validity of the requirements of normative-legal documents at the enterprise;
- case of control over the activities of financially responsible persons;
- implementation of the adopted government decisions.

In the analysis of the order on the accounting policy of the enterprise, the auditor will clarify the same: indeed, the fact that all items of the order are subject to the accounting policy; that all aspects of the accounting policy (organizational-technical, methodical, tax-related) are reflected in the order. In these matters, the audit staff will give appropriate advice and recommendations to the managers of the economic entities.

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